

War and Its Meaning as a Political Phenomenon

Artur Victoria

You will say, there has always been war, more or less cruel, sometimes bitter almost always brutal hence in conflict and in autonomous social clashes — the hordes, the tribes, the primitive and barbaric peoples, the illustrated and rich cities, the powerful states and the millennial empires, all animated by a more vigorous collective consciousness.

More tenuous, all aware of their existence as independent groups and also aware of the aspirations and interests common to all their members often conflicting interests and aspirations, if not antagonistic, concerning those who to other groups they inspired and united.

Since the first states were formed, under the archaic arena of the city-states that flourished and shone in the ancient world reappearing after in the dazzling terrain of the European Renaissance, from the great empires founded by religion or sword to the nation-states that still today between us multiply, when perhaps it already arises in embryonic forms.

Tomorrow's multinational structure, it has always been the states the true protagonists on the international scene, as authorized interpreters and paladins of the aspirations and interests of the corresponding social groups. It matters little that in authoritarian states - without any scum, in democracies - under disguises of greater or less consistency, often, if not always, present themselves as interests and aspirations of the collectivism, some that are after all, only a simple minority, better aware of its own objectives, well-equipped for political action and above all skilled in the management of multiple social controls - the so-called ruling elite.

Its ability to sensitize and attract the mass, the docilely under his effective leadership by the Attic charismatic force that awakens and assures the mimetic mechanism that Toynbee so well described, gives well the real measure of his creative power.

Whatever it is, however, seeking, really this elite or minority, translate the interests and aspirations still in a float inaccurate in the popular soul or go further and strive.

That the people understand and feel their true interests and aspirations dealing with Machiavellian or demagogically of mystifying the mass so that it adheres to its particular elite goals or coercing it into it after all accessory - the prime that is worth considering in the international scene as a whole It is that each state moves at the potent impulse of a core of aspirations and interests, more or less precisely defined in a hierarchical complex of Goals.

For the nation-states of today are their National Objectives. Among these Goals, it is evident. It is important for those concerned with the persistence of the whole social group, the state, and the nation as such - that is their survival in space and time, their autonomy from others, and their own economic and social development, for human societies.

As for all organisms of greater or less complexity, stagnation is death. According to the circumstances prevailing in each case, survival, autonomy, and development will translate into secondary objectives because of the conquest of foreign lands or the defense of one's own territory of aggression or peace, acquisition of wealth or safeguarding assets, attaining spheres of economic influence or liberation, cultural subjugation or nationalist affirmation, autonomy, irredentism, freedom or imperialism, domination — a whole range of political, economic objectives.) psychosocial and even military the unreliable aspirations and interests of the wise ruling minority.

Excited, like that each State by its own Objectives, and grounded them in a predominantly selfish moral code. No wonder there would be no different antagonisms, some of the vital importance, among certain States, for wanting these opposite things when not, each for themselves, the same thing, in this anarchic landscape that remains, despite all the efforts spent millennia in treaties and ever-short-lived leagues, international life on the planet.

And it is by seeking, to the relative satisfaction of the various stakeholders, these antagonisms between states that diplomacy arises with all its old arsenal of conciliatory practices, its formalism seemingly as ridiculous as it is useful, and the morning strategy that would make the lasting glory.

As result, there is the concept of National Security, understood in its broadest and most active meaning, gradually permeating the whole domain of state policy, conditioning when not promoting or determining any and all economic planning. , whether social or political. Not to mention the properly military plans of both war and peace. Nor could it happen otherwise, as long as the war is over.

It is no longer a mere tragic hiatus in a world of tranquillity and peace. When, at the time of the French Revolution and its great Napoleonic epilogue, it returned. in the scenario of Europe the war of nations, relegating to the musty archives the rococo style of the old dynastic wars, Jomini could see in it, at first, a violent drama of deep unleashed passions.

Nevertheless, this drama had a well-defined beginning and fortunately an end that could never be predicted.

Today the concept of war has been broadened and, not only as he complained and warmly advocated Ludendorff in a famous statement to all the territorial space of the

belligerent states, absorbing in the tremendous vortex of the struggle the entire economic, political, cultural and military effort of which it was capable of each nation, rigidly integrating all activities into one resultant one aiming at victory and victory only, confusing soldiers and civilians, men, women and children in the same sacrifices and identical dangers and forcing the abdication of secular freedoms and costly acquired rights in the hands of the state, almighty lord of war.

It has expanded even further, and not just to the full extent of world space, by appealing to all peoples and invading all continents, all seas and all skies, obscuring the legal figure of neutrality and equating belligerent and non-belligerent same trials in a maximum overflow that is unaware of any spatial limitations.

It has also expanded on the scale of time, incorporating pre-war and post-war in itself as mere attenuated manifestations of its overwhelming dynamism — larval forms of war, but deep down in the war.

From strictly military war it thus passed the total war, both economic and financial and political and psychological and scientific as the war of armies, squads, and airplanes: from total war to global war; and from global war the indivisible war and why not recognize it? Hitler's "white war" or Stalin's cold war is a substitute for peace and, in fact, it is no longer possible to distinguish where peace ends and where war begins - further evidence and it is from every disastrous angle, of the general confusion of values in which it is perilous to overwhelm the civilization of the western world.

To this ubiquitous war, all instruments of action, whether directed at a distance, are of equal value to him in achieving a victory that ultimately results in the effective attainment of the National Objectives and the complete fulfillment of aspirations or ambitions - just or unjustifiable. It matters little to the popular soul. victory as much less costly as it can come without the decisive but cruel use of force.

They serve you, so both exclusively politic weapons - diplomatic negotiations. more or less ostensible riches, pressures and interventions (is not abstention sometimes a form of intervention?), the alliance and counter-alliance game, the agreements and treaties in their public or secret clauses - like economic weapons - sanctions, loans and capital investments, exchange rate pressures, tariff policy and trade discrimination, the embargo, the boycott, the dumping.

From propagation and counter-propaganda, tempting ideologies, and suggestive slogans for internal or external use persuasion, blackmail threat and even terror make it one of the most effective weapons in its wide-ranging arsenal.

And it retains the military as a powerful asset that is so valuable today, an indispensable catalytic factor at the table of discussions like on the battlefields.

The Strategy, art before reserved to the mastery of the military leaders in the conduction of their campaigns having come of age, says Beukema, he rose. with all its valuable baggage of principles widely experienced from Marathon and Salamis, not to mention Timbra from Alexander and Caesar, not to mention Epaminondas, from Sun-Tzu and Vegetius and Guibert and Clausewitz to much higher planes, after all being characterized as a true national security policy.

Undoubtedly, Clemenceau had already predicted it when he famously stated that "war is too important a matter to be trusted entirely in the hands of the generals".

So we have, at the summit of National Security, a Strategy, by many called Great Strategy or General Strategy art of the exclusive competence of the government and which coordinates, within a fundamental Strategic Concept, all political activities. Economic, psychosocial and military objectives that concurrently aim to achieve the Goals which embody the national aspirations for unity, security and growing prosperity. This strategy is subordinated because both the Military Strategy and the Economic Strategy, the Political Strategy and a Psychosocial Strategy, which differ from each other by their particular fields of application and their own instruments of action although they never stop acting in solidarity be it in time or in space. Were it is not for the Strategy in the background like the war itself, indivisible and total.

Strategic Concepts that suggested to their respective governments:

Mahan - to affirm US hegemony in the western continent and the Far East. in the future to succeed England in world leadership. Corresponding policy for the creation of a short line between the two oceans through a channel well protected by a base belt, securing the undisputed dominance of the Atlantic and Pacific, maintaining a tacit alliance with England and opposing which wants expansionist pretensions from Japan.

Mackinder - Current Objective - To conserve British supremacy by preventing the emergence. on the continent, of a power capable of controlling the 'Heart of the World' '. Corresponding achievement policy - to prevent any alliance between Germany and Russia, establishing between both have tampon countries and the famous "sanitary cord."

- As far as the German geopoliticians, under the leadership of this amateur geographer who was Haushofer, they did nothing but take advantage of Mackinder's suggestive conception of defining a German strategy that met the uncontainable national aspirations for expansion exacerbated to paroxysm by the vivid and painful resentments of the 18th, the imbalance resulting from the great economic depression of the 30th, by a complex of dispossession — almost say castration — in the face of the sharing of the colonial world and no less an ambivalent sense of admiration and hatred of England undisputed sovereign of the seas.

These aspirations were not the geopolitics that created them; they came from a remote past, from the old masters of German idealist philosophy, from the testament of Frederick the Great. "The first principle of the art of government is to maintain existing power and, under the circumstances, to increase it and extend it more and more.

- from Nietzsche's theses full of vigorous nationalist ethos about superman and war "Loves peace as a means of preparing new wars and loves even more short peace than lasting peace" since Von Bernhardt and the unlimited overvaluation of violence and struggle, from the dream of rebuilding the former Roman Empire in Van den Bruck's Third Reich, Wagner's ultra-nationalist poems, "Volk ohne Raum" - people without space - Hans Grimm and the ambiguous "Blut und Boden" - blood and land or race and territory — until Spengler's apocalyptic message. For the time had come for Germany to take on the role of "great disturber" of the constituted international order.

If we admit the terminology proposed by Castex, however great his mistakes - and Reverend Walsh, his greatest enemy, sees in it more than fifty percent truth - Geopolitik faithful to the Germanic spirit and the deepest aspirations of the German soul.

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